

THE EFFECT OF PREFORMING QUALITY ON THE PERMEABILITY OF NON-CRIMP FABRICS AND THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THEIR COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In liquid composite molding (LCM), fabric reinforcements are formed on the mould firstly, and then impregnated by resin. The preforming quality of the fabric reinforcements, referring to the fiber angle changes and the occurrence of forming defects, can affect the subsequent injection process and the mechanical properties of the final components. In this paper, a type of carbon non-crimp fabric (NCFs) with tricot-chain stitches, was formed on a hemispherical mould with an annular blank holder automatically. By changing the blank holder force (BHF) applied on the fabrics during the stretching forming process, hemispherical preforms with different fabrication quality were obtained, where fiber angle changes were measured manually and forming defects were recorded. The results showed that the increasing BHF may slightly increase the shear angle. The main type of the process-induced defects may be inter-yarn gaps for NCF with tricot-chain stitches. The followed injection process was conducted to determine the correlations between the preforming quality and the permeability of the fabrics. It was indicated that the change of the fiber orientation and fiber volume fraction (V_f) leads to the variety of permeability along a certain longitude on the hemisphere. Finally, compressive tests were performed on the corresponding components. The results indicated that inter-yarn gaps mostly happened asymmetrically for the NCF with tricot-chain stitches. It leads to the resin-rich areas in the composites, which have a negative influence on the mechanical properties of the composite components as the origin of cracking.

1 INTRODUCTION

The traditional method to fabricate composite parts is to lay up the prepregs with the desired stacking sequence on the mould, and to cure the lay-up in an autoclave then. This process is costly and unsuitable to manufacture components with complex shapes. Liquid composite molding process has

gained increasing popularity in composite production over the past few years. It can generally take place in three major steps: fabricating the preforms, injecting the resin and curing [1]. When fabricating the preforming, especially for complex curved preforms with net shape, the reinforcements have to be fit the mould tool via such deforming as in-plane shear, compression and/or bending [2]. The non-crimp fabric (NCF) possesses a lot of advantages over traditional woven fabrics. It consists of unidirectional plies arranged in the designable orientations, which are bound together by the stitching yarns [3-4]. Due to the unique structure, it can take full use of the fibers' mechanical properties. Besides, the shear resistance of NCFs is usually lower than that of the woven fabric. For shear resistance in a certain direction, there is even no 'shear locking angle' for NCFs, which means that NCFs may provide excellent drapeability in making composites with complex shapes [4-8].

Hemispherical structure is a typical structure used to investigate the deformability of the textile reinforcements [9-12]. The main purpose of this study is for understanding the correlations between the deformation behavior and subsequent impregnation and mechanical behavior after forming the NCFs on the double curvature surface. In this paper, carbon NCFs with tricot-chain stitches were used to be formed on a hemispherical mould. With the change of the blank holder force (BHF), the draping defects were observed and the shear angles of the textiles along certain longitudes and latitudes on the hemisphere were measured as well. Moreover, the permeability of the NCF with tricot-chain stitches along the longitudes under the vacuum conditions were estimated according to the radial flowing test. The effect of the BHF on the permeability were also investigated. Finally, the mechanical behavior of the hemispherical composite were studied under the compression load.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Materials

Carbon NCFs with tricot-chain stitches used in this study were provided by Weihai Tuozhan Fiber Co. Ltd.. Their parameters, as specified by manufacturer, are shown in Table 1. The carbon fiber used here is a Chinese homemade fiber, CCF300 (3K), corresponding to Toray T300. The fabrics are stitched by polyester (PET) yarns with a weight of 33 dtex and areal density of about 2 g m^{-2} . The photographs of the NCFs are illustrated in Fig. 1.

Preform ID	Stitching pattern	Area density(g m^{-2})	Number of layers	Orientation of fiber tows	Stitching spacing (mm)	Needle spacing (mm)
CCF300 NCF	Tricot-chain	332	2	$0^\circ, 90^\circ$	2	2.5

Table 1: Parameter of the Non-crimp Fabrics

Figure 1: Photographs of NCFs: face (a) and back of NCF with tricot-chain stitches.

2.2 Experiments

2.2.1 Forming and shear angle measurement on a hemisphere

The fabric is put on the holder board with a blank holder on it, with a weight of 3.22 kg, corresponding to the pressure of 1.67 kPa, referring to low BHF. The various BHF, referring to middle and high level BHF, is to apply 10 N and 20N loads on the blank holder, respectively. When increasing the load further more than 20N, the stitches are likely to be broken during the draping process. The forming process is demonstrated in Fig.2 that a hemisphere with a diameter of 150 mm is slightly moved up, so that the fabric can be formed on it.

Figure 2: Schematic diagrams of hemispherical forming process.

Before forming, the points where shear angle is measured should be marked. A grid of white markers, with a 1 cm step from the center of the sample (330 mm×330 mm in size), is plotted along the direction of 0°, 45°, -45° and 90°. After forming, along the latitude line of 30° and 60°, markers are plotted from the longitude 0° to 180° in a step of 10°. The measurement points are shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Schematic of longitude and latitude directions on the hemisphere (a) and positions of measurement points (b).

2.2.2 Experimental estimation of permeability of NCFs for hemispherical infusion

The shear angle of the fabric is changed along with the longitudes and/or the latitudes on the hemisphere. Hence, the V_f is changed. Both the V_f and fiber angle have an impact on the permeability along the certain direction. The permeability along the longitudes, where the shear angle was measured, is estimated via recording the infusion process on the hemisphere. The infusion set-up is shown in Fig. 4. Silicon oil with the viscosity of 68 mPa s was used to impregnate the preforms. Time and corresponding flowing distance were recorded. It is approximately regarded as a radial flowing process as that under the in-plane circumstances. The flowing time is recorded for each marked point on the hemisphere. The permeability for each point is estimated by Eq. (2) [13],

$$K_x = \frac{\mu \cdot (1 - V_f) \cdot x_l^2}{4 \cdot \Delta P \cdot t} \left[2 \ln \left(\frac{x_l}{R_0} \right) - 1 \right] \quad (2)$$

where x_l is the location of the flowing front at the time t in a certain direction. V_f is the fiber volume fraction at the measured location, and R_0 is the radius of the injection port. ΔP is the pressure gradient.

The fiber volume fraction can be obtained by Eq. (3),

$$V_f = \frac{w_l \cdot n}{h \cdot \rho} \cdot 10^{-1} \quad (3)$$

where w_l is areal density of the fabric at the measured point, g m⁻²; n is number of the layers; h is the thickness, mm, and ρ is the volumetric density of the fiber, g cm⁻³. Considering the effect of shear deformation on the areal density of the fabric, the local areal density, w_l , which is used to estimate the fiber volume fraction for the permeability measurement, is calculated by the nominal areal density of fabrics, w , and shear angle θ as

$$w_l = \frac{w}{\cos \theta} \quad (4)$$

In fact, directly measurement of the local permeability on the hemisphere is very difficult. The

point-wise permeability estimated by the above method is averaged permeability for the flowing path from injection port to the measured point, since the permeability is continuously changed along the flowing path. Nevertheless, the averaged permeability calculated by Eq. (2) – (4) are helpful to understand the influence of draping on the subsequent infusion.

Figure 4: Testing set-up for permeability of NCFs on a hemispherical mould.

2.2.3 Mechanical test for hemispherical composites

Hemispherical composites reinforced by NCFs was fabricated via the process of vacuum assisted resin infusion (VARI). Six layers of (0°/90°) NCF were draped on the hemisphere surfaces separately by the tool as shown in Fig.2. Here two different draping conditions, including low level BHF and high level BHF were used to form different preforms, to investigate the effect of the draping condition on the mechanical of the composites. After draping, tackifiers were sprayed on the fabric to keep their shape. Then the fabrics were transferred to the die for resin infusion. A domestic epoxy resin used for fabricating the composites, named 3288, were provided by Beijing Institute of Aeronautical Materials. The resin were infused at 50 °C. After the reinforcement were impregnated, the mold was heated to 140 °C for 1 hour to cure the resin.

After demoulded, the composite were glued on testing base plate. Compression load were applied from the top at the rate of 1 mm/min. Strain gauges were stuck on the hemisphere along the latitude of 60° (Fig. 5). Testing points for the strain corresponds to the points where the shear angle was measured, as indicated in Section 2.2.1. At the measurement points, the strain along the longitude and the latitude were measured during the loading test.

Figure 5: Testing set-up of mechanical properties for hemispherical composites and schematic of the positions of the strain gauges.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Draping behavior of the NCF on a hemisphere

For the shear angle, the symmetrical shear deformations mainly occur along the longitude of 45° and -45° for NCFs with tricot-chain stitches. Along the longitude of 0° and 90°, the force is parallel to the fiber direction so that there is almost no shear deformation, as shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: Shear angle of tricot-chain stitching CCF300 NCF along the longitudes under different levels of the blank holder force: low level (a); middle level (b) and high level (c).

Since the stiffness of CCF300 fibers is relative low, increasing BHF may lead to more deformations of the fabric, to fit the mould. When increasing the BHF, the shear angle along each longitude is not increased obviously for NCFs with tricot-chain stitches. However, the increasing trend of shear angle can be seen when comparing the shear angle along the latitude under different BHF. The shear angle measured on the latitudes can be fitted to sinusoidal curves, as shown in Fig. 7. The amplitude of the fitted sinusoidal curves, which refers to the deformation degree, is listed in Table 2. The amplitude of the fitted curves for CCF300 NCF is gradually increased, which means more shear deformations occur in CCF300 NCF with the increasing BHF.

Figure 7: Shear angle of tricot-chain stitching CCF300 NCF along the latitude of 60° and 30° under different levels of the blank holder force: low level (a); middle level (b) and high level (c).

Amplitude (Deg.)	Blank holder force		
	Low level	Middle level	High level
CCF300 NCF	23.01 ±1.13	25.01 ±0.72	27.38 ±0.95

Table 2: The amplitude of the fitted curves for NCFs under different level of blank holder force.

Increasing the BHF is aimed to make the fabrics to fit the mould tightly. By observing the hemispherical preforms, it can be seen that there are noticeable inter-yarn gaps on the fabric, as shown in Fig. 8. During the stretch draping process used here, the fabrics were subjected to stretching force along each radial direction. Inter-yarn gaps, the main type of the draping defects, may happen when the stretching force is perpendicular to the fibers direction, during the stretch draping process.

Figure 8: Draping defects of the NCF with tricot-chain stitches.

3.2 Permeability of the NCF on a hemisphere

Fig. 9 shows the results of permeability calculated by Eq. (2) – (4) for CCF300 NCF with tricot-chain stitches. After forming the NCF on the hemispherical mould, it was found that both the fiber orientations and the fiber volume fraction were changing along a certain longitude from the apex to the equator of the hemisphere. Hence, the permeability is not a constant along the measured direction. Considering that the fabric is a type of symmetrical fabric with parameters of yarns in both warp and weft directions similar, permeabilities in directions of 45° and -45° are similar. And the permeability in 45° directions is slightly higher than that in 0° direction. It may be due to the relative fiber orientation. However, for all preforming circumstances, it is interesting to find that the permeability in the longitude of 90° is higher than that along other directions. It can be explained by the fabric architecture of tricot-chain stitching. Stretching draping method used here could incur significant gaps between the yarns in the face of the fabric along the direction of 90° , as shown in Fig. 8. Whereas, continuous stitching loops in the back (Fig. 1(b)) prevent the inter-yarn gaps happening in the direction of 0° , though there exists the same stretching load perpendicular to the fiber yarns. The inter-yarn gaps provide flowing routes for the liquid, remarkably facilitating the flowing along the direction. Besides, due to the stretching effect during the forming process, the dimensions of inter-yarn gaps should be increased with the increment of the BHF. Thus, the permeability is slightly enhanced when increasing the BHF.

Figure 9: Results of permeability for CCF300 NCF with tricot-chain stitches on a hemisphere fabricated under low level (a), middle level (b) and high level blank holder forces (c).

3.3 Mechanical behavior of hemispherical NCF composites

Two types of hemispherical composites were produced with the hemispherical preforms fabricated under different BHF. Fig. 10 shows the compression loading results for the composites. Before the sample was broken, the load-displacement curves for the two hemispheres are similar. However, the cracking load for the sample with low BHF is a little higher than that with high BHF. Besides, it is interesting to find that the cracking mostly occurred along the longitude of 90° for both the two cases, although the reinforcements is orthotropic, with the same amount of fibers in both directions of 0° and 90° . Hence, there may be process-induced changes happened for the preforms during the draping process. As mentioned in Section 3.1, inter-yarn gaps are the main draping defects of the NCF with tricot-chain stitches during the stretching draping process. By observing the hemispherical preforms fabricated under high BHF, it can be seen that there are noticeable inter-yarn gaps along the longitude of 90° on the fabric. Whereas, no obvious inter-yarn gaps occurred along the longitude of 0° , as shown in Fig. 11. It may be attributed to the stitching feature. The continuous stitching can bind the fibers along the direction of 0° , preventing the inter-yarn gaps happening under the transverse stretching force; while the stitching is not continuous along the direction of 90° , it is easy to induce inter-yarn gaps under the transverse stretching force.

Figure 10: Mechanical test results: the load-displacement curves of the composites with different preforming fabrication conditions (a) and photograph of the damaged sample (b).

Figure 11: Photographs for the hemispherical reinforcements formed under high BHF: obvious inter-yarn gaps along the longitude of 90 °(a) compared with those along the longitude of 0 °(b).

Fig. 12 shows the strain data measured during the mechanical tests for the composite fabricated under high BHF. Along the longitude, the negative values show the compression load; while the positive values along the latitude corresponds to the tensile strain. It is shown that the strain along the direction of 0 ° and 90 ° (the fiber directions) is lower than that along the bias directions. No matter for the fiber directions or the bias directions, the strain grew relatively symmetrically at the initial displacement. However, with the displacement increased further, the strain data indicated that early damage happened along the direction of 90 °, which corresponds to the observation on the damaged sample, shown in Fig. 10(b). As mentioned above, there are inter-yarn gaps along the direction of 90 °, which would result in the resin-rich area after manufacturing the composites. Therefore, the early cracking happened at these weak positions.

Figure 12: Strain measurement results for hemispherical composite fabricated under high BHF: strain along the longitude (a) and along the latitude (b) at different measuring positions.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Preforming quality is important to the properties of the final composite components. The objective of this paper is to understand the influences of fabric architecture and preforming quality on the

processibility of reinforcements and mechanical properties of composites, when fabricating double curvature parts with non-crimp fabrics (NCFs). The blank holder force (BHF) have no significant impact on the shear deformation for the symmetrical NCFs with tricot-chain stitches. However, increasing the BHF may gradually incur more inter-yarn gaps on the NCF. Due to the stitching configurations, inter-yarn gaps occurred asymmetrical for the NCF with tricot-chain stitches, though the fibers of fabric are symmetrically orthotropic. Inter-yarn gaps mostly happen in the direction of 90°, which results in a promotion of the permeability. In addition, these defects lead to resin-rich area and early cracking for the composites in this direction.

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